

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

DISPOSAL OF SPENT IONIZATION RADIATION SOURCES COBALT-60

Ashrapov U.

PhD, senior researcher, Institute of Nuclear Physics of Academy Sciences, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Mirzaev B.

PhD, senior researcher, Institute of Nuclear Physics of Academy Sciences, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Nesterov V.

PhD, Chief Specialist, JSC «Research Institute of Technical Physics and Automation», Moscow, Russia

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7032324>

Abstract

The article discusses the experience work of specialists of the consortium as part of the INP AS (Tashkent, Uzbekistan), JSC " JSC «Research Institute of Technical Physics and Automation»" and CJSC "Mounting Firm "Rady" (Moscow, Russia) at utilization of 96 pieces of sources GIK-7-2 Co-60 of gamma installations of "RKHM-gamma-20" and "Issledovatel", including 2 emergency sources Co-60, their burial in specialization point for radioactive waste. Also, the experience of specialists in the elimination of emergency situation with recharge a highly active source of GIK 8-4 Co-60 for radiation gamma therapy from emergency holder with crack to a new holder from depleted uranium. The reason for the appearance of a crack on the body of the Co-60 source holder is discussed.

Keywords: radionuclide Co-60, emergency situation, gamma-installation, ionization radiation source holder, depleted uranium, radioactive waste.

1. Introduction

Radiation technologies in scientific research, irradiation of materials and foods, gamma therapy in oncology is based on use gamma-radiation of closed source of ionizing radiation with radionuclide Co-60, which has a half-life of 5.2714 years and very hard energy of gamma radiation (1.732 and 1.3325 MeV). Sealed sources GIK 8-4 and GIK 7-2 Co-60 belong to dangerous radioactive sources of category 1 [1] and if safety rules are not observed or their protection is not reliable, they can cause irreparable harm to human health and the consequences can be fatal.

There are 16 large medical institutions in Uzbekistan with devices for radiation gamma therapy with Co-60 sources for oncological dispensaries, as well as a gamma installation with GIK-7-4 sources at the INP AN in Tashkent and a gamma installation GUBE-6000 of the Veterinary Research Institute with GIK- 7-2 in Samarkand region. Currently, the actual tasks are the utilization of expired Co-60 sources, and the related training of personnel to work with Co-60 sources, the development of technologies, special instruments and equipment used for their disposal. To work with high-level sources of Co-60, a consortium was created consisting of specialists from JSC "NIITFA", CJSC "MF" Rady "and the Institute of Nuclear Physics of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the purpose of which is to utilize sources of ionizing radiation Co-60 GIK 8-4 and GIK 7-2 and eliminate emergencies with them.

The article is aimed at presenting the experience of the consortium in the elimination of accidents with high-level sources of Co-60, as well as their disposal.

2. Materials and methods

Gamma-installations «RKHM- γ -20» and «Issledovatel» of JSC «Foton» were designed to conduct radiation research in the field of solid state physics, radiobiology, medicine and production and technological processes for gamma irradiation of semiconductor products. The assigned life of Co-60 sources has expired six times, however, the total activity of 96 pcs. sources of Co-60 GIC 7-2 in both gamma installations was $2.056 \cdot 10^{13}$ Bq (555.4 Ci).

To discharge Co-60 sources from gamma-ray plants, a reusable transport packaging kit UKT-1V-26-12 with a rechargeable container KTB-250-12 was used (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Scheme of the transport packaging kit UKTIV-26-12: 1 - KTB-250-12 rechargeable container; 5 - cover of the protective container; 2 - drum; 6 - body of protective packaging; 3 - cork; 7 - thermal protection.

In Table 1 are shown specifications of the UKTIV-26-12 packaging kit.

Table 1. Technical characteristics of the packaging kit UKT1V-26-12.

Facing	Steel type X18H10T
Protection	lead
Maximum container dimensions	diameter – 680 mm, height – 860 mm
Nest dimensions	diameter - 14 mm, height – 105 mm
Weight, kg	2320
Number of working channels	12
Permission loading sources Co-60	up to 25 kCi

Installations "RKhM- γ -20" and "Issledovatel" are lead containers, in the center of which there are working chambers located around the circumference with tubular cassettes ("squirrel wheel"), each of which

could accommodate up to 6 GIK 7-2 sources Co-60 with dimensions: $\text{Ø}=11.2$ mm, $h=81.5$ mm. Fig. 2 shows the structural diagram of the "Issledovatel" gamma installation [2].

Fig. 2. Structural scheme of the "Issledovatel" gamma-installation: 1 - bed; 2 - counterweight; 3 - stock; lead container (radiation head); 5 - work table; 6 - cylindrical irradiator; 7-beam shutter; 8-shutter body; 9-cork; 10-lift mechanism; 11 - blocks; 12- cables.

For the removal of GIK 7-2 Co-60 sources from the «RKhM- γ -20» and «Issledovatel» gamma-installations, standard collets and rod rigs were used. Fig. 3

shows a general view of the collets, rods and non-standard tools for removing 2 emergency Co-60 sources.

Fig. 3. Photo view of the collet (a), rod (b) and developed a new non-standard tools (c) for the removing 2 emergency Co-60 sources.

Non-standard tools are hollow tubes with pointed ends that attach to a drill and do the job of removing the epoxy around the Co-60 source.

The specialists with DPG-03 thermo luminescent dosimeters and «Rados Rad-60» (Radiation Safety Associates Inc.) dosimeters were provided. Dosimetric control of the exposure dose rate by dosimetric device IdentyFINDER R400 (USA) was carried out. The radiation-hazardous work of the personnel was carried out under constant dosimetric monitoring of the radiation level in compliance with sanitary standards and radiation safety requirements (SanPiN # 0193-06) [3].

3. Results and discussion

The consortium performed work on the radiation-safe mode of unloading 96 sources of Co-60 GIK 7-2, including 2 emergency sources from the gamma-ray installation "Issledovatel", they were transported by special vehicles during 4 times (total 560 km) from JSC "Photon" (Tashkent city) to the Republican State Enterprise for the Disposal of Radioactive Waste (settlement Aydarali, Tashkent region) accompanied by a police convoy and were buried in the storage of spent radioactive sources. An emergency situation is present when discharging from a gamma plant 2 emergency sources of Co-60, which are present in the hardened epoxy

resin. In this emergency situation, standard equipment could not be used, so a non-standard tool was developed. Fig. 4 shows the use a non-standard tool for removing emergency sources 2 that were in the hardened

epoxy resin and specially designed tools were used to destroy the epoxy resin (a).

Fig. 4. Destruction of epoxy resin (a), removal of emergency Co-60 sources from the «Issledovatel» gamma-installation (b), dismantling of the KTB-250-12 recharge container with Co-60 sources (c).

Another joint work of the consortium was the elimination of an accident with Co-60 radiation ionization source in an emergency holder of a gamma therapeutic remote apparatus in the Namangan Regional Oncological Dispensary, where the emergency situation arose due to a jamming in a transport and reloading container of the KTP-5M type of a clip with radioactive cobalt-60 of the GIK 8-4 type with an activity of 3750 Ci. The holder together with the source could not be removed from the rechargeable container using standard technology, which required the return of Co-60 to

the manufacturer from the Russian Federation. Emergency situation by the personnel using special equipment with remote manipulators in a protective box of Republican central isotope laboratory was resolved. In the protective box, the holder with the Co-60 source was removed through the inlet channel using remote manipulators, the source was transferred to a new holder, which was then placed in the KTP-5M container in accordance with the flow chart (Fig 5).

Fig. 5. Preparatory work with recharge container KTP-5M (a) and recharging of the Co-60 source from the emergency holder into a new holder in protective box (b).

The dosimetrically measurements on Radiagem-2000 radiometer and gamma spectrometric measurements immersion liquid on DSA-1000 digital multi-channel spectrum analyzer with Genie-2000 software (Canberra, USA) were carried out.

The exposure dose rate (EDR) on the surface of the recharge container KTP-5M was 10.8 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$, while the EDR in the working room was 0.25 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$. After

removing the Co-60 source from holder, a visual inspection of the holder body showed the presence of two longitudinal cracks on its surface, as a result of which the holder body swelled and increased by 0.94 mm in diameter, which led to a problem with its removal through the outlet channel of the container for recharging. Fig. 6 shows crack on the body of source holder.

Fig. 6. Crack on the body of the source holder.

However, a crack in the body of the holder did not lead to a violation of the tightness of the Co-60 source itself, the tightness of which was checked by the immersion method [4]. The gamma spectrometric analysis data of immersion liquid was showed that the Co-60

source is sealed because activity of immersion liquid is $\leq 185 \text{ Bk}$ [5]. The method of dry and wet smears of radioactive contamination on the body of the holder was not detected.

Often there are emergencies with containers containing an alloy of depleted uranium (radiation heads of gamma flaw detectors, protective and transport containers).

Fig. 7. Depleted uranium container (a) containing a source of Co-60 and a plug of depleted uranium that was completely wedged into the body of the container during expansion (b).

The emergency situation could be eliminated and the container lid with radiation ionization source of Co-60 opened only by repeatedly exposing the plug to alternating low temperature with liquid nitrogen (-196 °C) and high flame temperature with a gas burner (+500 °C).

When analyzing the cause of a crack in the depleted uranium holder body or jamming of the depleted uranium container cap, it was concluded that in the presence of oxygen, water vapor can be adsorbed on the walls of the holder with depleted uranium, which reacts violently with uranium with the release of hydrogen, which reacts with uranium to form pyroform uranium hydride [6]. As a result, the lid of the depleted uranium container swells or a crack occurs in the body of the container.

The ongoing chemical reactions can be represented by the following equation:

As is known, the density of depleted uranium is 19 g/cm³, therefore, with the complete oxidation of uranium due to oxygen and moisture from the air, a two-fold increase in the volume of the holder is possible. The cause of corrosion in the body of the holder is the thermodynamic instability of the metallic state of depleted uranium. It should be noted that the IAEA classifies depleted uranium as category II nuclear material and defines the levels of physical protection during storage and transportation [7], which means that precautions must be observed when handling depleted uranium products.

4. Conclusions

In the total 96 pieces of exhausted Co-60 sources from the «RhM-γ-20» and «Issledovatel» gamma-installations at the appointed time and in compliance with radiation safety were discharged and utilized as radioactive waste. Non-standard emergency with the removal of two emergency sources of Co-60 from the gamma installation successfully was completed [8]. The IAEA news reported on the successful completion of the international project [9].

The highly active source Co-60 GIK 8-4 from the emergency holder into a new holder of the gamma therapeutic installation was recharged. Replacement of the

depleted uranium holder with a new one guarantees its further performance for 15 years.

The results of many years of work with depleted uranium products have shown that hydrolysis corrosion is observed in majority depleted uranium products used for radiation protection against gamma radiation (radiation head of gamma flaw detectors, transport packaging containers and protective containers for high radioactive closed radiation ionizing sources).

References:

- Code of Conduct on the Safety and Security of Radioactive Sources. 2004. Vein. IAEA. 24.
- Gamma-installation "Issledovatel". 1969. Technical description and instructions of operation. Moscow. 30
- Radiation safety standards and basic sanitary rules for ensuring radiation safety. 2006. SanPiN No. 0193-06. Tashkent. 92.
- Ashrapov U.T., Ergashev Kh.A., Makhkamov Sh.M. 1997. Leak test method source of ionizing radiation. Patent of the Republic Uzbekistan. # 4943.
- Radionuclide ionizing radiation sealed sources. Leakage test methods. 1992. International Standard ISO 9978-92. Washington. USA. 11.
- Karnozov A.A. 2000. Issues of protection of fissile materials in nuclear charges. Solving the plutonium problem. Digest of articles. JSC "High-tech Research Institute of Inorganic Materials named after Academician A.A. Bochvar". 92-97.
- The Convention on the Physical Protection of Nuclear Material. 1980. Information Circular of the IAEA. <https://www.iaea.org/sites/default/files/infcirc274r1.pdf>
- Ashrapov U.T., Doroshenko A.A., Nesterov V.P., Tashmetov M.Yu., Filatov K.V. 2017. Elimination of emergency situations with highly active sources of cobalt-60. Questions nuclear science and technology Moscow. 76. 53-56
- IAEA. 2016. News of the scientific portal "Atomic Energy 2.0" <https://www.atomic-energy.ru/news/2016/05/20/66073>